

Corporate Culture for Organisational Performance: A Literature Review

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Abstract

This is a review of corporate culture for organisational performance. Relevant literature pertaining to corporate culture and organisational performance were synthesised, providing a framework for a broader understanding of the current state of the corporate culture. The literature review comprised various published journals on the subject matter, with emphasis on the conceptualisation and types of the corporate culture. After a review of a wide range of relevant literature, it was discovered revealed that corporate culture has a strong influence on organisational performance; for an organisation to perform effectively and efficiently there must be a clear communication framework, consistency and stability and, employees should be given the opportunity for innovation through training, indoctrination and research to enhance performance. It was recommended that business managers should ensure that there is a clear communication framework, consistency and stability in corporate culture; employees should be given the opportunity for innovation through training, indoctrination and research for an organisation to perform effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: Communication, corporate culture, norms, performance

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Introduction

The longevity of any corporate entity is largely dependent on its performance, which is largely a result of how organisational goals are achieved effectively and efficiently. It is observed that the pattern of values, norms, beliefs, attitudes and assumptions guiding the behaviour of its workforce in achieving these set goals play a pivotal role in this milieu. In the organizational performance milieu, corporate culture is said to be the most important variable (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014). This is because, people are always cocooned in culture and this constitutes the background for the working experience, serving as a powerful mechanism for controlling behaviour. One visible tendency of corporate culture is to bind the workforce together and provide a direction for the company.

Corporate culture is the silent assumptions about how work is done, the behavioural dos and don'ts, supported or not supported by an organisation (Eric, 2010). It refers to the set of values, norms, beliefs, attitudes and assumptions that may be unwritten but moderates the behaviour of workers within an organisation and how they do things. This makes an

organisation different from another organization (Armstrong 2020; Ortega-Parra & Sastre-Castillo, 2013). It gives direction concerning the way employees complete tasks and interacts with each other in the workplace. Corporate culture should be used for measuring the performance of an organisation through employee attitude in the workplace as it predicts how people perceive their work environment through their visible and conscious practices (Hofstede, 2011)

Despite the many positive benefits of organisational culture, it is perceived that poor communication and inconsistency are some issues bedevilling its contribution to performance. Poor communication results when understanding is not mutual; a discrepancy between the message sent and the decoder results in ineffective communication. It is widely reported that organisational culture is not properly communicated or understood. Again, inconsistency in the organisational culture may send conflicting messages to employees. Where norms are not long term and consistent, it will result in a half-hazard implementation and create confusion in the organisation. Following the introduction, the study proceeds with a review of literature in section two, the methodology is addressed in section three, findings in section four, conclusions in section five, with recommendations in section six.

Literature review

Corporate culture

Amah and Daminabo-Weje (2013), view culture as the principal system of beliefs, values and norms, upheld by organizational members, and handed down to new members. Thus, culture plays a major role in employee commitment and performance. Corporate culture is a set of values, beliefs, behavioural patterns which within the subconscious propels workers in choice-making as well as decision making. Wahyuningsih, et al., (2019), views organisational culture to be the norms an organizational member observes at the place of work and how norms affect the behaviour of workers in their adaptation to organisational objectives. According to Simoneaux and Stroud (2014), it is the way members of an organization interact among themselves and other parties with a vested interest in the organization. Kamau and Wanyoike (2019), opines that adapting externally, survival together with integrating internally is the rationale for culture.

Fundamentally culture is established through sharing of learning processes premised on the proper allocation of resources (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014). Hence, the performance of an organisation is affected by the collective behaviour of its workforce which is a derivative of its corporate culture. For example, organizations having primarily internal process culture could strongly resist reforms that promote innovation (O'Donnell & Boyle, 2018). Adequate knowledge of corporate culture and typology explains variations in impacts of managerial reforms internally and between organisations. Kumar (2016) concludes that corporate culture has direct effects on the organisation and workers as well as aid in determining employee

turnover and job performance. Warren Buffet, listed global richest entrepreneurs, stated that organisational culture is crucial in driving performance (Childress, 2018).

Organizational culture can emanate from many sources for instance beliefs and assumptions of founding fathers (Flamholtz & Randle, 2017) or through the learning experience of organizational members. O'Reilly et al. (2018) developed a method of measuring organizational culture using six factors namely adaptability, integrity, collaboration, result orientation, customer orientation and detail orientation. Four major types of corporate culture exist - clan or supportive culture, adhocracy culture, hierarchy culture, and competition culture (Fiordelisi & Ricci, 2014; Mousavi, 2015; Wiewiora et al., 2014). There are discussed as follows:

1. The clan or supportive culture: This cultural type values human affiliation, collaboration, attachment, trust, loyalty, and support (Fiordelisi & Ricci, 2014). Nando and Ikyanyon (2018) added that managers also encourage employees to be engaged and committed to organisational goals because such employees carry out their tasks effectively and fulfil responsibilities assigned to them.
2. Adhocracy or entrepreneurial culture: the adhocracy culture is also referred to as the entrepreneurial culture. Innovation and change are held as crucial enhancers of organizational performance (Fiordelisi & Ricci, 2014). Corporate management adopting an adhocracy culture allocate greater resources to research and development and motivate workers to go after innovation (Sokro, 2017). Veisheh et al., (2014) said that organisational members in this type of culture require precise direction for their tasks and the significance as well as the effect of such tasks on organisational goals. The value of adhocracy culture is held by assumptions like continuous growth, taking risks, being creative, diversifying, being independent, and the ability to adapt.
3. Hierarchy culture: the main thrust here is the need for rules and regulations in managing organisational activities (Sokro, 2017). Coa et al. (2015), presented that workers follow the rules and regulations of hierarchy culture. Here every operation is done with predefined procedures and rules, clarity in communication, consistency, and stability. The aim of this culture is efficiency and effectiveness (Mousavi, 2015).
4. Competition or market culture: this type of culture involves gathering information on competition and customers, proper goals setting, planning and decision-making, leaders focused on tasks, aggressive marketing and drive to achieve. Miguel (2015) held that the key components of market culture are communicating openly, competing, ability to achieve and being competent. To succeed in this culture, corporate managers must know their clients and market preferences. Another pressing goal of corporate management in market culture is the satisfaction of equity holders through large income, large market share, large margins, quick growth and productivity (Sokro, 2017). When the organisational culture is effective, managers utilize the values, behaviours, and strengths of employees to sustain the organisation and enable it to compete in the marketplace.

Organisational performance

The concept of organizational performance is associated with the sustainability and success of an organization (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014). This will comprise the actual performance as against the projected performance. Kamau & Wanyoike (2018) found that performance is the aggregate of accomplishments achieved by all the departments of the organisation. According to Moon, et al., (2019), performance means the act of things being done and used, giving attention to conditions, processing, communicating and results being achieved. It is not static but active. Ali, et al., (2018) describes performance as four-dimensional: behaviour, standards, support and inter-relationships. An organization that performs highly will have a culture that makes workers accountable and responsible for meeting customers' needs in time to make sure the business succeeds (Onyeze et al., 2015). An organisation cannot perform well in the absence of these four layers.

Methodology

An exploratory method was used for the study. This was done by a review of related literature which provides an understanding of the concept. This methodology is adequate as it stimulates more research and debate on the subject matter. Three central databases were used to search for the literature – Google Scholar, ERIC and ProQuest Databases. Keywords such as “organisational culture”, “organisational performance”, “institutional culture”, “organisational effectiveness” and so on were toggled to ensure that relevant literature were sourced. Boolean operators such as double asterisks (**) and quotation marks (“”) were used to obtain a broad spectrum of search results after a mean key work (for asterisks) and to ensure that the search results are adequately filtered based on a specific string or strand of phrases (for inverted commas). The initial search yielded a total of 89 search results across the three databases. After checking all the files, duplicated materials/contents were all removed. This reduced the number of literature materials from 89 to 66. The researchers read through the abstracts of the 66 materials and found that even though the contents of 44 materials focused on organisational culture or performance, they were not focused on the business sector. Consequently, they were removed, resulting in 22 literature materials that met the criteria for selection. The full texts of the 22 pieces of literature, considered relevant for the study were read and integrated to the current study (where applicable).

Results

Majorly, the results in majority of the cited studies tend to reveal that for an organisation to perform effectively and efficiently there must be a clear communication framework, consistency and stability in corporate culture. This is affirmed specifically by the study of Coa et al. (2015) presented that organisational members follow rules and regulations as depicted in

hierarchy culture. Here tasks are done by predefined ways and rules, backed by clarity in communication, consistency, and stability.

Employees should be given the opportunity for innovation through training, indoctrination and research. It is through innovation that business owners can then be satisfied when high revenue, market share and profits are generated. This is corroborated by Sokro (2017), that business managers should allocate large resources o research and development and motivate workers to innovate.

Conclusion

This study presents a synthesis of relevant literature on the effect of corporate culture on performance. Sequel to the findings above, it is concluded that corporate culture is considered an essential ingredient of organisational performance. In addition, organizations should ensure that there is a clear communication framework, consistency and stability with predefined procedures and rules. More so, if organisations will thrive, organizations should prioritise culture-building activities such as training, indoctrination research and innovation amongst its employees, this will boost the corporate culture and hence its organisational performance.

Recommendations

The recommendations below were made following the result observed in the literature:

1. Business managers should ensure that there is a clear communication framework, consistency and stability in their corporate culture for their organisation to perform effectively and efficiently.
2. Business managers should allocate sufficient resources for employee innovation through training, indoctrination and research to increase performance.

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